

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

IMPROVING THE ACCURACY OF EXPLORATION OF OIL AND GAS RESERVOIRS BY INDUCTIVE COUPLED PLASMA MASS SPECTROMETRY

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Abstract

It was determined that some fluids saturated with carbohydrates from the upper layers of the earth's mantle entered the deposit. In addition, a number of experiments show that the number of extracted hydrocarbons (HC) and the remaining part is consistent with the increase in the number of substances transferred to the deposit. Experiences show that the concentration of hydrocarbon gases increases with increasing depth in places where oil and gas deposits are suspected, and the composition of the gas becomes very close to the composition of the deposit as it approaches the deposit. The process of dolomitization can change the volume and structure of rocks to such an extent that it can also cause changes in the reservoir properties of that deposit. At any stage of the development of productive deposits, change can occur at any time. Previously, it was very difficult to confirm the existence of a direct relationship between saturated HCs and rocks (especially at low temperatures). Because at that time there were no devices with high sensitivity and high resolution. However, the emergence and development of mass spectrometers played a huge role in the study of the elemental composition of rocks. The analysis of rocks by means of ICP-MS proved once again that it is possible to obtain the vertical distribution of some elements by studying the element composition of cores taken from different depths of oil and gas fields. It is possible to increase the accuracy of oil and gas deposits by knowing the concentration of these vertically distributed elements.

Keywords: oil and gas fields, fluids, hydrocarbons, mass spectrometer, geochemical method.

1. INTRODUCTION

For many years, the so-called "direct" method has been used to determine the deposits of hydrocarbons (HC) with high accuracy. This method is based on the detection of the characteristics of the region where oil and gas deposits are located. Although the history of direct methods is more than 40 years, the gradualness and accuracy of the application of this method did not fully meet the specified criteria. However, the main reason for using this method was that high-precision methods in this field have not yet been widely used. Therefore, 2-3 out of every 10 exploratory wells were productive at best.

Currently, the forecasting of oil and gas fields is possible by direct method in two ways:

1. Conducting search-excavation works (underground geology) since ready-made geological maps and products (cuts, mineral compositions of rocks, etc.).

2. Localization of discovered oil fields with the help of terrestrial or remote mobile, direct methods, and seismological works.

Although direct methods have the above-mentioned advantages, it is very difficult to ensure the accuracy of predictions made by this method. Depending

on the application area and geographical location, their detailing through these methods is different. According to the calculations of individual authors, the points where the shooting is carried out are different in every km or km². For example, it is possible to use "direct" methods in known and unknown locations of the results of exploration wells.

Currently applied exploration methods are based on the analysis of oil and bituminous substances, hydrocarbon gases, solid rocks, and concentrated areas of rocks [1]. Currently, at the initial stage, the presence of hydrocarbon gas is checked by gas logging at a depth of 50 m in the upper layer [2].

Later, the study of hydrocarbon formed due to the migration and accumulation of different parts of the earth's layer and anomalous accumulation by geochemical method took an important place. At that time, the main issue was the change in the composition of the migrated hydrocarbon rocks. Such measurements appeared due to the development of new methods and tools. Currently, methods of studying the composition of some rocks at the molecular and atomic level have been developed. [3].

This method is widely used because geochemical indicators carry enough information in the search and exploration of oil and gas deposits.

The article shows the possibility of the wide use of inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometers for geochemical data processing to increase the accuracy of predictions in the exploration of oil and gas fields.

2. METHODOLOGY OF EXPERIMENTS

The experiments were carried out by the inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometric method. At this time, argon plasma was obtained at the expense of atmospheric pressure and argon gas, and the analysis of elements was carried out with the help of a quadrupole mass analyzer [4,5]. This method has recently been widely used in studying the composition of rare and scattered elements. The choice of argon gas used as a working gas at this time is explained by the fact that the ionization potential of substances in the cycle system of elements is lower than the single ionization potential of argon. This reason allows us to analyze 80% of the known elements in nature. The main advantage of this method is its sensitivity and wide dynamic range.

An inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer is commonly used to study water-soluble substances. During the study of solids, samples are first dissolved in acid. Usually 2-5% nitric acid is used for this. At this time, the amount of the sample in the solvent should not exceed 0.2-3% [6].

At present, two methods of sample preparation are used in the analysis of elements by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometric method of geological objects: direct dissolution method [7,8], and acid mineralization method [9,10].

The direct solution method has several advantages: simplicity, expressivity, low cost, minimal risk of additional contamination of the sample, etc. The shortcomings are frequent breakage of rubber hoses, blockage of the atomizer, extinguishing of the plasma torch, blockage of the holes of the sampler and skimmer, etc. Despite these shortcomings, the direct method of sample preparation is becoming more and more widespread in practice.

Note that the composition of solvents varies from method to method. Nevertheless, the solvents used during the analysis of geological objects consist of more

complex mixtures. For dissolving cores, mainly nitric acid, or ammonia solutions, ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDS), sometimes there are geological objects, for example, quartz element, which is used only in HF (fluoric acid), which directly affects some parts of the device, mainly cones. For this, nickel cones (sampler and skimmer) are replaced by titanium cones, which is due to the high resistance of hydrofluoric acid.

But each of these acids (mixtures) has its own specific role. Thus, hydrofluoric acid protects the atomizer and igniter from contamination, which is beneficial when the sample concentration does not exceed 0.01% by volume. EDS protects the walls of the device from adsorption and desorption; 1-butanol prevents the interference of the argon element with the Se isotope (this happens only due to the formation of the ArC^+ ion). Ammonia dissolves heavy elements, nitric acid stabilizes the shape of elements, sometimes increases their adsorption on the device wall when its concentration exceeds 0.5% by volume. In this case, it is enough to settle the solution in a centrifuge before analysis.

Repeating the rinsing process (multiple times) also facilitates the dissolution process. Usually, the sample is diluted 10 times. Diluting the sample several times (20-50) protects the interface system entrance of the device from organic substances and salts.

Sample preparation by acid mineralization (in a microwave oven) differs from other methods in terms of complexity, significantly greater time and material waste, additional contamination of the sample and reduced risk of loss of volatile elements. Also, one of the most widespread methods of decomposition of samples with acid is the use of a microwave field (microwave oven) [11-13].

The SpeedwaveXpert microwave oven (Figure 1) makes dissection simple and safe. The unit operates at a boiling temperature of 200-240 °C and a pressure of 30-60 bar to dissolve samples with a mass of 0.2-0.5 g. In the process of splitting the sample, it provides temperature and pressure control with the help of special sensors that do not disturb the system area in the microwave oven.

Step	Time	T1	T2 ⁽¹⁾	p ⁽²⁾	Power
1	00:15:00	200°C	110°C	45 bar	Max power*
2	00:15:00	200°C	110°C	45 bar	Max power*

(1), (2) Optional sensors

Figure 1. BerghovSpeedwaveXpert microwave core melting software.

3. RESULTS AND THEIR DISCUSSION

To carry out the research, core samples were obtained from the AzLab laboratory of SOCAR. Core samples taken from different oil and gas fields of the country and from different depths were studied by means of ICP-MS. To protect the confidentiality of the information provided, we will mark each oil and gas field with the appropriate letters.

Figures 2 and 3 show the elemental composition of cores taken from different depths of deposits A and B by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry. As can be seen from Figure 2, Mg, Cu, Zn, Sr, and In elements were detected in the cores taken from the A field at depths of 487, 538, 600, 671, 704 m, and the concentration of these elements was observed to increase as the depth increased. Figure 3 shows an increase in the concentration of two elements Al and Fe in the cores taken from the depths of 765, 800, 824, and

832 m of the B deposit. This shows that deposit B is a deposit rich in Al and Fe elements. A very high concentration of Mg element was found in both deposits at a depth of 500-800 m. This shows that the Mg element increases the probability of detection even at depths of 800-1000 m. Since the concentration of Cu element in the B deposit is greater than in the A deposit, it indicates that the dolomitization process is going on there more strongly. This means that the collector property of the rocks in the B deposit is stronger.

It can be concluded from the conducted experiments that while all deposits are rich in common elements Mg, Al, Cu, and In, some areas have very small concentrations of Zn and Fe elements in some areas. It can be seen from the pictures that the concentration of all elements increases depending on the depth, which once again proves that the dolomitization process is taking place in these cores.

Figure 2. Elemental composition of cores taken from different depths of deposit A.

Figure 3. Elemental composition of cores taken from different depths of the B deposit.

Dolomitization is the main factor of hydrocarbon deformation-metasomatic transformation of the deposit. Deformation and metasomatic transformations of rocks usually include their secondary rock transformations. Although there is enough information about the effect of tectonic and depth fluids on the hydrocarbons of the deposit, until now there is almost no information in the literature about the effect of their properties on the filtration process of rocks [14]. Many researchers point out that tectonic activation processes fluids to the upper layers of hydrocarbons, so far, the changes in the filtration properties of rocks during the development of the field have not been sufficiently studied. Many researchers have proven that tectonic activity causes some fluids saturated with carbohydrates in the upper layers of the earth's mantle to enter the deposit. In addition, several experiments show that the number of extracted hydrocarbons and the remaining part is consistent with the increase in the number of substances transferred to the deposit.

Thus, the change in the number of HC substances in the bed due to the decrease in pressure there shows that [15] the change (mainly growth) of void phases in the rocks is due to the decrease in capillary pressure there. However, such studies do not consider the movement of fluids in layers. However, this change can lead to changes in the dimensions of those spaces due to the formation of repeated rocks.

Special studies show that the amount of HC reserve formed due to HC passing through the upper mantle is the same as the amount of the above-mentioned substance.

It should also be noted that dolomitization occurs very quickly in calcareous rocks, which highlights its collector feature.

Finally, let's note that the dolomitization process can change the volume and structure of rocks to such an extent that it can also cause a change in the collector properties of that deposit. At any stage of productive deposits, changes can occur at any time [16].

The mechanism of changes in the composition and properties of rocks under the influence of migrating gases has been little studied, both on the basis of theoretical and practical materials. Indeed, it was quite difficult to confirm the existence of a direct connection between saturated HCs and rocks (especially at low temperatures). Because at that time there were no devices with high sensitivity and high resolution. However, the emergence and development of mass spectrometers played a huge role in the study of the elemental composition of rocks. The analysis of rocks by means of ICP-MS proved once again that it is possible to obtain the vertical distribution of some elements by studying the element composition of cores taken from different depths of oil and gas fields. It is possible to increase the accuracy of oil and gas deposits by knowing the concentration of these vertically distributed elements. This shows the productivity of 3 and 4 of every 10 drilled wells, which saves 20-30% of the funds spent on drilling.

4. CONCLUSION

Investigation have shown that:

1. The method of geochemical exploration of oil and gas fields is based on the interaction of hydrocarbons with rocks during the vertical migration of hydrocarbons (HC) rising from the field. Currently, both the physicochemical and the composition of the rocks change considerably.

2. During the geological period (hundreds of years) because of tectonic processes, a vertical (sometimes super-vertical) migration path is formed for many fluids, and highly mineralized water migrates upwards. At this time, as a result of the change reaction, Ca and Mg ions enter the crystal lattice of carbonate ions and form dolomite $\text{CaMg}(\text{CO}_3)_2$. Currently, the collector property of rocks increases and the concentration of migrated hydrocarbon gases in them increases.

3. Carbon dioxide plays a major role in changing the properties and composition of rocks. As a result, the concentrations of Ca, Si, Mg, Na, K, Fe, Ni, Cu, and other elements that make up the rocks change.

4. Since the conducted studies, it is possible to obtain information about the degree of change of the rock forming the cross-section of the bed and the nature of the distribution of carbohydrates there. At this time, cores taken from different depths of oil and gas deposits are studied for their element composition using an inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer. Based on the depth concentration of the received elements, the accuracy of the exploration of deposits increases.

5. One of the main issues to be studied at the next stage is the change of physical and chemical properties of rocks (or HCs) by known methods. By this or other methods, it is possible to determine the migration zone of fluids migrating from the field and in this way increase the accuracy of the prediction of field exploration.

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